

Comparative Analysis of The DLSU and NOPSSCEA Member Schools' Sports Programs

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Abstract:

The study determined to gauge the extent of implementation of school sports programs of DLSU and NOPSSCEA member schools. This is a descriptive study utilizing researcher-made questionnaire to test the extent of implementations of the two aforementioned sports programs. MANN-Whitney U was used for the significant difference of the extent of implementation of school sports programs. The extent of the implementations of school sports programs of De La Salle University (DLSU) as a whole showed very great extent and Negros Occidental Private Schools Sports Cultural Educational Association (NOPSSCEA) school members showed great extent. As a whole, there is a significant difference in the extent of implementation of the sports programs of DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members. However, in terms of the extent of recruitment and incentives and rewards in the implementation of their sports programs, no significant difference was noted. It is recommended that school administration and sports managers of NOPSSCEA school members should improve their sports programs and intensify the implementation specifically in terms of trainings to be given to the sports personnel concerned. The physical fitness training and training analysis must be given importance and emphasis to build an environment of empowered student-athletes thereby ensuring their maximum involvement through a proposed school sports program.

Keywords: Comparative analysis, School Sports Program, De La Salle University, NOPSSCEA

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Sports engagement is a natural pastime for virtually all the people in the world. Nelson Mandela (2001), the famous South African president states that "Sport has the power to change the world. It has the power to inspire. It has the power to unite people in a way that little else does. It speaks to youth in language they understand. Sport can create hope where once there was only despair. It is more powerful than government in breaking down social barriers. It laughs in the face of all kinds of discrimination." Sports can be viewed as a product of, and a window on culture that can serve as "a vehicle for the manifestations of those norms and values fundamental to the culture of the society within which it is performed" (Blanchard, 2000). Distinction has also been made between what constitutes modern sport, and studies on the origins and meaning of sport have established that the term sports emerged in England only during the times of the Industrial Revolution (Crowther, 2007). Diversely, sport as a phenomenon has transformed since antiquity (McClelland, 2007). This word has been referred to just how sport is acknowledged today. It could mean a deep-rooted, formally administered viable physical activities wherein members are driven by internal and external recompenses" (Coakley, 2009). A more detailed description penned and spearheaded by UNICEF (2004), which was utilized in the Olympic Kit of the International Olympic Committee (IOC) sketches sport as "any type of physical activity that presents to physical fitness, mental well-being and social interaction.

These comprise play; recreation; casual, organized or competitive sport; and indigenous sports or games." The comparative analysis of sport comprises the making of assessments and contrasting between facets of sports

culture, provision and organizational structures in different countries. It forms a component of a range of academic programmed involving sport and leisure. Although the use of comparative study as a means of improving policymaking is a valuable endeavor, the concern is less with comparative analysis for policy and more concerned with the importance on the documentation and clarification of alterations between local dogma organizations, processes and outcomes. One commonly used method to the proof of identity and clarification of differences between local rules regimes is using typologies which not only excites argument of the comparative prominence of specific command features, but also allows the construction and taxing of premises. Hence, one of the most convincing influences all for relative local policy inquiry is that there are certain features of rule managements that can best be discovered over and done with the acceptance of a relative method. Proportional strategy investigation may consequently be defensible as a tactic that pursues to find and authenticate its assumptions as a consequence of hypothetically well-versed assessment between local policy commands (Keman, 2002).

Sport is a global, rapidly growing industry. The sport industry is composed of organizations that are involved in sport. A large number of different types of organizations make up the sport industry, including amateur sports, professional sports, sporting goods manufacturers, sport goods retailers, public assembly facilities, sport management consultants, sport agencies, etc. Whether it is a freestanding industry or segment of the entertainment industry, sport is a multibillion-dollar business. Governing bodies are an important part of the sport industry. Any given governing body is structured in a way to achieve its stated mission within the environment in which it works. The aim of this study was to compare and analyze the DLSU sports program with that of NOPSSCEA school members' sports programs. This study is also deemed to introduce a sports development program that may improve probable weakness in both agencies' sports programs.

Current State of Knowledge

The sports industry has been increasingly growing and its social and economic development impact has been recognized internationally (Swinnen and Vandemoortele, 2008). They added that sports affect a person's physical development and also his or her social and psychological development has effects in society development both socially and economically. It was the reason why the United Nations organized the international Year of sport and physical Education in 2005 and incorporated sports into its programs and policies. According to Andrett and Szymanski (2006), sports are increasingly important to the economy that has about 2 million people are employed in sports industry in 15 member countries of the European Union which is almost 1.3% of the overall EU employment.

The sports significance is experienced in all levels of the society ranging from individuals, organizations and nation at large. The countries which have higher achievements in sports are made known to the trading partners internationally. More and more investors pay more attention to the countries with good sport performances in the particular category (Ferkins, 2010). For example, in sports, various sports football clubs in England have attracted investors from outside the country. Manchester United investors are from America, Chelsea from Russia, Manchester City investors are from Qatar. In order to realize such sports success, the country needs to have good sports programs which are the product of good sports policy along with strong National Sports Associations to lead such sports' development programs. Good sports administration, appropriate strategic plans, a good national sports policy and appropriate coaching (Professional) programs all together have positive impact towards country's sports development (Omari, 2002).

The efficient and effective administration makes the sports program to be vibrant and future promising where, as the poor, inefficient and ineffective administration provides uncertain sports future. However in the last ten years, the standard of sports has been declining considerably and has raised concern among Tanzanians. In the World cup football Tanzania currently (2012) ranks above the 100th position according to the FIFA World ranking which is a worse position. In CHAN competition Tanzania has not succeeded to lift the cup since its participation in 2009 (www.tff.com). In the World Cup competition since it started in 1930 Tanzania has never qualified for FIFA World cup finals played in various countries (FIFA, 2013). In Olympics Tanzania again has failed to show the winning spirit in any competition in 2012 (www.tanzaniasports.com). Generally the situation in Tanzania is not promising and there is a debate in trying to find out reasons as well as causes of the decline in the performance of clubs and the national team.

Many departments that have inadequate facilities, equipment and manpower surprisingly perform well because of the ability of their administrators. A good sports administration contributes directly to the nation's excellence in the development of sports (Omari, 2002). For the sports program at the school to bear the intended results, there must be a well-rounded education system which enhances children's sports interest to help them involve in sports activities (Omari, 2002). This needs to go hand -in-hand with good sports policy, well organized systems, good relationships among the sports stakeholders/sports activities and well qualified sports administrators. These aspects if well designed from the grassroots level, in particular at school level, to the national level, the achievements of sports in social and economic development will be realized.

Planned sports promotion is the method of planning and employing undertakings for the advancement and dissemination of a sports provision to the consumer, the result of which pleases the clients needs and the institute goals ("Sports Marketing", 2014), this effects in an on-going planned appropriate flanked by the aims and resources of the group and continually varying prospects (Stolar, 2008). Sports are a cutting-edge form of play. Even though play may be limited in some ways as it abstracted as sport, it must keep in mind many of the characteristics, (it is a voluntary and has time boundaries). Sport is essential to our culture. There are those who are involved in sport in an educational, recreational, or professional capacity. Sports are also integral pointer of the health and vivacity of our culture. A suggestion of the alleviating and entertaining purposes of sport in culture is seeing when persons are involved in sport in positive and rewarding ways. Because sport is an integral part of our culture, students should learn as the subject matter of physical education should be development of skills and strategies necessary to participate in sport. Participation in sport should be modifying to contribute to the students understanding and ability to play sports successfully. A physically educated person is one who has learned to play and appreciate sports more completely, to coordinate and manage their own sports more completely, to coordinate and manage their own sport experience, and to (accept) individual responsibility and (demonstrate) group membership skills. Getting men involved in sports may make them more likely to stay rather than drop out of college completely; however, it may also make them more likely to go elsewhere. Getting women involved in sports may not only make them more likely to stay, it may make them less likely to go elsewhere (Leppel, 2005). The NCAA defines its basic purpose (Bylaw 1.31), the competitive athletics programs of member institution designed to be vital part of the educational system. A basic purpose of this association is to maintain athletics as an integral part of the educational program and the athlete as an integral part of the student body and by doing so retain a clear line of demarcation between intercollegiate athletics and professional sports.

Theoretical Underpinnings

This study is anchored on Utilization-Focused Evaluation (UFE) Theory developed by Michel Quin Patton, Ph.D. in 2013. This theory states that "evaluation should be judged by their utility and actual use. This theoretical model is applied when the end goal is instrumental use (i.e., discrete decision-making). To engage primary intended users, the evaluator must identify stakeholders who have the most direct identifiable stake in the evaluation and its results, in other words, the 'personal factor' (Patton 2013). In particular, this study made an analysis on the school sports programs, hence the researcher identified the primary stakeholders as the school sports program coordinators or managers, the athletes, the coaches and other sports personnel in the evaluation of their school sports programs, specifically those of DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members.

In addition, Empowerment Evaluation Theory is perceived to have an overarching support to the framework of this study based on its tenets of fostering program improvement through empowerment and self-determination (SD). This theory was developed by David Fetterman, Ph.D. in 2012. SD theory describes an individual's agency to chart his/her own course in life and the ability to identify and express needs. Fetterman believes that the evaluator's role is to empower stakeholders to take ownership of the evaluation processes as a vehicle for self-determination. The evaluator engages a diverse range of program stakeholders and acts as a "critical friend" or "coach" while guiding them through the evaluation process.

In this case, the researcher, as she conducts the survey, stands as the evaluator acting as a "critical friend" in her analysis of the sports programs of DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members. The researcher guides the stakeholders of the sports program to examine their recruitment, training, rewards/incentives and tournaments/invitational engaged in, hence empowering them to take a look at what is the current situation of their sports program as to the aforementioned aspects and examine what should be improved. Empowerment evaluation seeks to increase the probability of program success by providing stakeholders with the tools and skills to self-evaluate and mainstream evaluation within their organizations. Fetterman (2012) outlines three (3) main steps for conducting empowerment evaluation: 1) develop and refine the "mission", 2) take stock and prioritize the program's activities, and 3) plan for the future, which the researcher aids in her sports program proposal.

Objectives

This study was conducted to assess the sports program of DLSU in comparison to that of NOPSSCEA school members' sports programs as the basis for NOPSSCEA sports program development. Specifically, this study sought to answer the following queries:1) the sports program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA School Members; 2) the extent of implementation of the sports program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members in terms of recruitment, training, rewards/incentives, tournaments and invitational and as a whole; and, 3) the significant difference in the extent of implementation of the sports program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members in terms of recruitment, training, rewards/incentives, tournaments and invitational and as a whole.

Methodology

This section discusses the research design used, the participants of the study, the instruments used, the data-gathering procedure, and the statistical treatment of data.

Research Design

The researcher used quantitative descriptive comparative analysis. Descriptive research is used to obtain information concerning the current status of the phenomena and to describe what occurs with regards to conditions or variables in a situation (Eugene, 2015).

Respondents

This study utilized purposive sampling – choosing DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members' sports programs for analysis. Purposive sampling occurs when the researcher consciously selects subjects to include in the study. Those selected by the researcher are information-rich case or those from which a lot can be learned. Researcher may make effort to include typical or atypical cases. The participants from DLSU were 5 coaches, 10 athletes and 1 sports coordinator for a total of 16. The participants from NOPSSCEA were 30 coaches, 200 athletes and 9 sports coordinators for a total of 239. The schools under NOPSSCEA were: Colegio de Sta Ana de Victorias, Colegio San Agustin Bacolod, John B. Lacson Colleges Foundation Bacolod, La Consolacion College Bacolod, Riverside College, Inc., Southland College Kabankalan, STI West Negros University, University of Negros Occidental Recoletos, University of St La Salle Bacolod and VMA Global College. To facilitate ethical considerations, the researcher used codes for NOPSSCEA school members such as school A,B,C,D... and so on.

Instruments

To obtain necessary data for this study, the researcher used a self-made questionnaire. It was subjected to validity (4.56-excellent) and reliability (0.89-reliable). All of them were interpreted as worthy and good, respectively. The questionnaire is made up of four components: recruitment, training, rewards/incentives and tournaments and invitational. There were 38 items in the said questionnaire. The response format employed a 4-point Likert – type scale. 1 for Strongly Disagree, 2 for Disagree, 3 for Agree, and 4 for Strongly Agree.

Data Gathering Procedure

Preceding the actual data collection, letters to the heads of each system school was sent requesting for the NOPSSCEA member schools' participation and cooperation for the study. Individual letters were sent to the sports coordinators and coaches during the NOPSSCEA Technical meeting held at VMA Gym. In addition, an email to the sports director of DLSU, Ms. Joy Lanting was also sent to seek permission to allow the conduct of the said study to the coaches and athletes. Individual letters to the athletes and coaches were given out during UNIGAMES 2018 to fill out the survey form. The questionnaires were retrieved within a period of 2 weeks.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 also used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the sports program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA School Members.

Objective No. 2 likewise used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean to determine the extent of implementation of the sports program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members in terms of recruitment, training, rewards/incentives, tournaments and invitational and as a whole.

Objective No. 3 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U test to determine significant difference in the extent of implementation of the sports program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members in terms of recruitment, training, rewards/incentives, tournaments and invitational and as a whole.

Ethical Considerations

The participants of the study were voluntary. This means that those who were requested to participate in the evaluation of sports program were free from coercion. Participants were free to withdraw their participation at any time without negatively impacting on their involvement. It was a challenging task to encourage the participants to become engaged in the data gathering; however, the researcher exhausted all means to convince them to participate. It is the right of the participants to leave a program of this nature at any time; therefore no pressure was being placed on those who choose not to continue. Explanations of not continuing were also not required.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data gathered in connection with the objectives of the study and analyses of these data facilitated by the identified appropriate statistical tools. It interprets the results derived from the analyses.

Table 1

Extent and Rank of Implementation of the Sports Programs of DLSU and NOPSSCEA School Members in Terms of Recruitment

Item	NOPSSCEA Schools		DLSU	
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank
• Athletes from high school	3.44	1	3.56	5
• Sports you have completed	3.43	2	3.56	5
• Recruited online based record	3.34	6	3.25	9
• Head coach assessment for selection of athletes	3.39	3.5	3.38	7.5
• Qualified athletes undergo try outs	3.36	5	3.63	2.5
• Behaviorally based interview	3.31	8	3.69	1
• Assessment center	3.11	10	3.13	10
• Cognitive ability test	3.16	9	3.38	7.5
• Aptitude test	3.32	7	3.63	2.5
• Personality inventories	3.39	3.5	3.56	5
Overall Mean	3.32		3.48	

Legend: 3.41-4.00 Very Great Extent (VGE) 2.81-3.40, Great Extent (GE); 2.21-2.80, Moderate Extent; 1.61-2.20, Less Extent(LE); 1.00-1.60, Very Less Extent(VLE)

Table 1 shows the extent and rank of implementation of the sports program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members in terms of recruitment. As a whole, DLSU recruitment scored very great extent (M = 3.48) with the exception of assessment center, recruited online-based record, head coach assessment for selection of athletes, and cognitive ability test. As a whole, NOPSSCEA school members obtained a mean score of 3.32 interpreted as great extent. This implies that the sports program of both NOPSSCEA and DLSU in terms of their recruitment is to a high considerable degree of implementation. In NOPSSCEA, athletes from high school ranked first, whereas; in DLSU, behaviorally based interview topped the rank based on the mean scores.

Many student athletes dream of continuing to play their sport at the collegiate level. From football and basketball to swimming, baseball, softball, and more, there are a number of sports in which student athletes can be recruited to play at the next level, but it is important for students to understand the basics of the athletic recruiting process of a school before deciding if it is an avenue they want to pursue. Just as it is in the typical college search process, recruitment is a two-way street. Students need to learn everything they can about certain athletic programs and colleges in order to find the best fit, and those colleges need to market themselves so that students will be aware of their athletic offerings. A coach can't build a team without engaged student athletes, and those athletes can't be engaged without knowing the ins-and-outs of the formal recruitment process.

Table 2
 Extent and Rank of Implementation of the Sports Program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA School Members in Terms of Training

Items	NOPSSCEA Schools		DLSU	
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank
•Athletes off season training	2.96	1	3.75	5
•Athletes on circuit training	2.55	8	3.89	1
•Athletes on physical fitness training	2.48	9	3.88	2
•Athletes undergo mentoring program	2.60	5.5	3.31	8
•Athletes on psychological training	2.67	2.5	3.25	9.5
•Athletes on endurance training	2.66	4	3.25	9.5
•Athletes undergo training analysis	2.40	10	3.81	3.5
•Develop training and learning goals	2.57	7	3.81	3.5
•Designing training	2.67	2.5	3.69	6
•Athletes undergo specific training per event	2.60	5.5	3.50	7
Overall Mean	2.58		3.60	

Legend: 3.41-4.00 Very Great Extent (VGE) 2.81-3.40, Great Extent (GE); 2.21-2.80, Moderate Extent; 1.61-2.20, Less Extent(LE); 1.00-1.60, Very Less Extent(VLE)

Table 2 shows the extent and rank of implementation of the sports programs of DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members in terms of training. As a whole, NOPSSCEA obtained a score of 2.58 interpreted as moderate

extent. On the other hand, the DLSU, as a whole, obtained a score of 3.60 interpreted as very great extent. NOPSSCEA scored moderate extent to item numbers 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9 and 10. Items 3 and 4 scored less extent. This implies that the physical fitness training and athletes undergoing training analysis are not given enough focus. Athletes' off-season training ranked first in NOPSSCEA, while athletes on circuit training topped the rank in DLSU based on the mean scores. The DLSU sports program scored very great extent in items 1,2,3,7,8,9,and 10, which denotes that a very high degree of considerations or focus are given to the athlete's training while items 4,5, and 6 on mentoring, psychological and endurance training are of moderate extent.

In any field of competitive sports, conditioning and fitness are tantamount to success. For insofar as athletes go head-to-head with equal skill and talent, conditioning may very well spell the difference in determining who comes out on top. Following the recent successes of DLSU's athletes in the UAAP, Celis takes pride in ensuring that they are in top form whenever they compete in their respective sports (Alegre, 2017). To be a better athlete does not necessarily mean that one must train harder or longer. It could mean that this needs to address all the components that make up a successful athletic performance - mental as well as physical. Since one does not enter into competition with a completely empty head, he/she must include mental skills in training and conditioning programs as well. This will enable athletes to develop the strategies which will prepare them to enter a competition with the "proper mindset". According to athletics training.com (2019), as the science of sport performance evolves, it becomes increasingly important to integrate the mental and physical aspect of performance. Traditionally, no attention has been given to the cognitive aspects of performance. Coaches and athletes have devoted most of their attention to the physical components of performance. The secret to DLSU's winning moments in 2012, 2013, & 2015 were attributed to its intense training and discipline why they ruled the UAAP for the past three years, and these are also the keys for the continued dominance of their school's sports programs.

Table 3
Extent and Rank of Implementation of the Sports Program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA School Members in Terms of Incentives/Rewards

Item	NOPSSCEA Schools		DLSU	
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank
• Athletes offered a full grant scholarship	2.84	10	3.50	6
• Receives financial rewards	3.04	9	3.50	6
• Indirect financial rewards	3.26	8	3.63	3
• Tuition reimbursement	3.29	7	3.38	10
• Health insurance	3.51	2	3.44	9
• Flexible work schedule	3.35	6	3.44	9
• Disability insurance and life insurance	3.48	3	3.63	3
• Discounted program fees	3.57	1	3.69	1
• Family job offerings	3.46	4	3.50	6
• Time off benefits	3.45	5	3.44	9
Overall Mean	3.33		3.51	

Legend: 3.41-4.00 Very Great Extent (VGE) 2.81-3.40, Great Extent (GE); 2.21-2.80, Moderate Extent; 1.61-2.20, Less Extent(LE); 1.00-1.60, Very Less Extent(VLE)

Table 3 shows the extent and rank of implementation of the sports programs of DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members in terms of incentives/rewards. As a whole, NOPSSCEA obtained a score of 3.33 interpreted as great extent. The DLSU obtained a score of 3.51 interpreted as very great extent. "Discounted program fees" topped the rank both in NOPSSCEA and DLSU based on the mean scores. As far as full grant of scholarship and financial incentives, NOPSSCEA schools showed great extent. This implies that the scholarship and monetary incentives are of considerable degree only. On the other hand, DLSU's sports program showed that all items are of very high considerable degree of implementation (Jerusalem, 2015). This may mean that in terms of incentives/rewards, DLSU sports program exceeds that of NOPSSCEA school members' sports programs.

Under the Student-Athletes Protection Act, only the following benefits and incentives may be given by a school to a student-athlete: discounts on tuition and miscellaneous fees, full board and lodging, school and athletic paraphernalia, reasonable monthly allowance to be standardized and set by the athletic associations, medical and other similar benefits to further enhance the athletic and academic abilities of student-athletes (Jerusalem, 2015).

Any other benefits or incentives extended by the school to the student-athlete or his immediate family members are prohibited by the law and the violators of this provision may face penalties and sanctions by the Department of Education (DepEd) or the Commission on Higher Education (CHED) (Jerusalem, 2015).

Table 4
Extent and Rank of implementation of the Sports Program of DLSU and NOPSSCE School Members in Terms of Tournament/Invitational

Items	NOPSSCEA Schools		DLSU	
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank

• School level intramurals	3.47	4	3.50	5
• Extramurals	3.38	7	3.44	7
• National games	3.54	3	3.81	8
• University games	3.39	6	3.56	2
• International games	3.42	5	3.63	1
• Interschool tournaments	3.31	8	3.44	7
• Age group category tournaments	3.54	3	3.50	5
• Commercial league(open category tournaments)	3.57	1	3.50	5
Overall Mean	3.46		3.55	

Legend: 3.41-4.00 Very Great Extent (VGE) 2.81-3.40, Great Extent (GE); 2.21-2.80, Moderate Extent; 1.61-2.20, Less Extent(LE); 1.00-1.60, Very Less Extent(VLE)

Table 4 shows the extent and rank of implementation of the sports program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members in terms of tournament/invitational. Result proved that both DLSU and NOPSSCEA, as a whole, showed very great extent. This implies that as far as tournaments and some invitational, both DLSU and NOPSSCEA excel to a high considerable degree. Commercial league or open tournament ranked first in NOPSSCEA, while international games topped the rank in DLSU based on the mean scores. The participation of NOPSSCEA schools to different tournaments and invitational has made great impact to the lives of the student-athletes and has brought honors and glory to the schools. NOPSSCEA's contribution to Negros Occidental and Western Visayas Sports could not be taken for granted because for many years NOPSSCEA has contributed about 60-70% of the Negros delegation to the Palarong Pambansa.

NOPSSCEA has, likewise, contributed many athletes that donned the National uniform in International Competitions in Football, Track & Field, Swimming, Volleyball, Basketball, Sepak Takraw, Softball, Table Tennis, Cycling, Golf, Shooting and Archery (NOPSSCEA.org). For most student-athletes of DLSU, playing on the biggest stages and being adored by thousands of fans is but a dream. Whether being on a basketball court receiving a pass from Jeron Teng in the dying seconds of a do-or-die game against Ateneo, or being a part of the towering defense behind the net with Mika Reyes, or even taking a penalty shot for the DLSU Men's Football team, moments like these have always been the goals of many students sports enthusiasts. Aside from academic conferences, seminars, and other social events, various professional student organizations in the University now host sports tournaments catered to their members and even non-members (Jerusalem, 2015).

Table 5

Extent and Rank of Implementation of the Sports Program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA School Members as a Whole

Programs	NOPSSCEA Schools		DLSU	
	Mean	Rank	Mean	Rank
• Recruitment	3.32	3	3.48	4
• Training	2.58	4	3.60	1.5
• Rewards/Incentives	3.33	2	3.60	1.5
• Tournaments and Invitational	3.46	1	3.55	3
Overall	3.17		3.53	

Legend: 3.41-4.00 Very Great Extent (VGE) 2.81-3.40, Great Extent (GE); 2.21-2.80, Moderate Extent; 1.61-2.20, Less Extent(LE); 1.00-1.60, Very Less Extent(VLE)

Table 5 shows the extent and rank of implementation of the sports programs of DLSU and NOPSSCEA school members as a whole. Result proved that as a whole, DLSU showed very great extent. However, NOPSSCEA school members as a whole showed great extent on the implementation of their school sports programs. This implies that the school sports program of DLSU's sports program is excellent and next in rank comes the NOPSSCEA school members in their sports program excelling to a high considerable degree. Tournaments and invitational ranked first in NOPSSCEA while training and rewards and incentives topped the rank in DLSU based on the mean scores.

School sports programs should aim to instill a positive attitude that can really change the outcome of any situation and will encourage the students to believe in themselves as well as others. These programs allow students to grow as an athlete and evolve as a person. It is important for athletes to take pride in what they do but it is also important to be humble in victory. Winning is not everything and schools will take a unique approach in teaching the student athletes the correct way to participate in sports activities.

Table 6

Significant Difference in the Extent of Implementation of the Sports Program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA in Terms of Recruitment, Training, Rewards/Incentives, Tournaments and Invitational

Program	Category	Mean	Mann-Whitney U	p-value
• Recruitment	NOPSSCEA	3.32		
	DLSU	3.48	1580.500	.230
• Training	NOPSSCEA	2.58		
	DLSU	3.60	130.500	.000*
• Rewards/Incentives	NOPSSCEA	3.33		
	DLSU	3.51	1308.500	.033*
• Tournaments and Invitational	NOPSSCEA	3.46		
	DLSU	3.55	1652.000	.351
Overall	NOPSSCEA	3.17		
	DLSU	3.53	342.500	.000*

If $p < 0.06$, then Reject H_0

Table 6 shows the significant difference in the extent of implementation of the sports program of DLSU and NOPSSCEA in terms of recruitment, training, rewards/incentives, tournaments and invitational. Results showed that in terms of recruitment, and tournament/ invitational, there is no significant difference. Therefore, the hypothesis is accepted. This means that the difference in the recruitment and tournaments and invitational of both the DLSU and NOPSSCEA cannot be compared because of insufficient evidences. In terms of training, rewards and incentives, there is a significant difference. This implies that DLSU, which has higher mean score, shows that their training and incentives and rewards are far different than that of NOPSSCEA school members. The overall result shows that there is a significant difference in the extent of implementation of school sports program between DLSU and NOPSSCEA. This implies that the implementation of DLSU is also different from that of NOPSSCEA school members.

NOPSSCEA's training should be given more emphasis and focus. There is a need for a holistic approach to athlete preparation that would make them more competitive in the world stage. Aside from the right training, the need for proper diet and psychological readiness are necessary to work together to enhance performance. The member schools must prepare the athletes for the pressure of competing on a global scale and do all that they can to provide them the necessary tools and skills to ensure victory since this area is considered the weakest point of NOPSSCEA's sports program. In addition, member schools should also enhance and improve their incentives or benefit programs to their student athletes specifically the scholarship grants. This will help promote excellence in sports by providing for the welfare of student athletes, coaches and trainers competing for various events and particular benefits and incentives for those who have brought honor and recognition to the school by winning in big competitions.

The DLSU's recruitment process should likewise be improved in order to promote fair recruiting environment. They may also try recruiting through mailed or emailed material or through social media.

Conclusions

Based on the analysis of the data, the researcher came up with the following conclusions: DLSU's implementation of their school sports program is better than what NOPSSCEA school members presently have. This is visibly shown in the output in UAAP performances of the DLSU. This further implies that most of their success is attributed to the kind of sports program that they have. With the results of the study, the researcher recommends the following: 1) the school administration and sports managers of NOPSSCEA school members to improve their school sports programs and intensify the implementation specifically in terms of trainings. The physical fitness training and training analysis must be given importance and emphasis to build an environment of student-athletes empowerment and involvement where they can offer their best; 2) the NOPSSCEA member schools' sports coordinators and coaches must be given the opportunity to undergo seminars and training with coaches from the UAAP schools; 3) the student-athletes must also be given the same opportunity for tune-up games with schools participating in UAAP to help them build a culture between NOPSSCEA and UAAP that embraces performance; 4) the only opportunity for NOPSSCEA schools to compete nationally is through UNIGAMES, so it is likewise recommended for the NOPSSCEA officials to consider competing in the UAAP; and 5) future researches on the same field of sports programs are recommended with more variables included.

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